

TOP 10 innovative trends in pharmaceuticals

ТОП-10 инновационных трендов в фарме

Farmatsevtika sohasidagi TOP 10 innovatsion tendentsiyalar

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Abstract: Pharmaceutical business relies more on innovation and research than other types of business, because this is the secret of success. How is the industry changing under the influence of digitalization, customization and biotechnology today? And what will it be tomorrow?

Keywords: Pharmaceutical industry, international organizations, business processes, biotechnology, innovation, pharmaceutical companies.

The pharmaceutical industry is a collection of state institutions, private businesses, international organizations that open, develop, produce, sell and control the quality of drugs and medicines (pharmaceuticals). The 19th century, with its focus on chemical synthesis, marked the beginning of the modern era of the pharmaceutical industry. Before that, for millennia, people relied on the medicinal properties of plants, substances of animal origin (as well as the animals themselves) and minerals. The twentieth century marks the synergy of chemistry and physiology, which has expanded the understanding of the basic processes of research, the discovery of new molecules, formulas and the invention of drugs. Today, the pharmaceutical industry is constantly discovering a variety of drugs for the prevention and treatment of even the most complex diseases, while simultaneously overcoming the challenges of the modern market - high competition, difficulties in certification and registration of medicines, tightening of control rules by regulatory authorities, requirements for strict confidentiality of information and pressure from consumers.

The pharmaceutical business invests in R&D much more capital than business in any other industry - about 15%. However, the pharmaceutical industry still lags far behind in innovation. The main reason is that pharma is tightly controlled by regulators to ensure the safety of medicines. In addition, most pharmaceutical companies have very strict internal rules that do not allow data exchange with other market players, thus depriving themselves of the benefits of a profitable partnership. This significantly slows down the business processes of any pharmaceutical company and the industry as a whole.

In times of high market turbulence and rapid change, it is not enough for a pharmaceutical company to focus solely on the sale of drugs and pharmaceuticals. Today, the industry is striving for a more holistic approach with integrated pharmaceutical and healthcare services, customization, and sustainable values that can drive lifestyle change. This predetermines trends and tendencies to which pharmaceutical companies must either actively respond or gradually disappear from the market. The presented 10 innovation trends do not cover the full spectrum of opportunities for the pharmaceutical industry of the future, but they allow you to learn how the industry is changing under the influence of digitalization, customization and biotechnology.

1. Prevention over cure

For centuries, people have sought to find a "magic pill" that could heal from various diseases and guarantee a long and safe life for millions. The trend of a healthy lifestyle, a fashion for harmonious development, a healthy, beautiful body and stability of the psycho-emotional state, access to an unlimited amount of information made it possible to successfully prevent certain diseases due to the correction of lifestyle and habits. This global trend has affected the pharmaceutical industry as well. Now more than ever, pharmaceutical companies are actively developing and offering dietary supplements and pharmaceuticals aimed at prevention: if some diseases today are not yet treatable, then their symptoms or fatal consequences can be prevented with the help of drugs.

A recent example is Truvada, the first approved pre-exposure prophylaxis drug from Gilead: a pill that could stop the HIV epidemic, as the press wrote about it. Pre-exposure or pre-exposure prophylaxis of HIV (or PrEP, Pre-exposure prophylaxis,) is a method that can significantly reduce the risk of possible infection with the virus through the prophylactic intake of highly active antiretroviral therapy by people at risk who do not have HIV. PrEP has not yet become widespread in the world, but clinical studies have shown that daily use of PrEP drugs by HIV-negative people reduces the risk of HIV infection by at least 40% - up to 73%.

2. Back to nature: biological laboratories

"Pharmacy" as a term comes from the Greek word φάρμακον, meaning medicine and the use of medicines. In ancient Greece, pharmacy, that is, pharmacy, was devoted to the study of the healing properties of plants and minerals. Only significant progress in chemistry has allowed pharmacists to change the vector from biological research to the study of the properties of individual elements and synthesized substances. Therefore, the pharmaceutical industry has developed as a part of pharmacy, directly related to the production and technological problems of the process of manufacturing drugs and substances. Several years ago, some scientists noticed that the pharmaceutical industry tends to ignore the diversity and possibilities of the natural world. Plants continue to be a source of biologically active ingredients that, if studied more deeply on their effects on the body, can provide important knowledge about the treatment and prevention of many diseases. Countries with unique flora can become pioneers of the establishment of a new botanical trend in the search for unknown medicines. For example, Amina Gurib, a biologist and the sixth President of the Republic of Mauritius, spoke about the amazing secrets of humble plants in her lectures at TED more than once.

3. Breakthrough innovation

Reversible innovations imply a return to a certain initial state in the event of an insolvency or non-compliance of the innovation with the new conditions of use. Realizing the potential of such innovations in the pharmaceutical industry is expected primarily from developing countries. Once introduced in a different developing country context, reversible innovation will spread around the world as a recognized technology or effective solution. Breakthrough innovation can provide an alternative choice to huge R&D spending for countries and companies that cannot afford huge R&D budgets. They are a response to the many challenges facing the pharmaceutical industry today: slowing successful innovation, rising research costs, declining revenues due to patent expiration, and the huge costs of bringing drugs to market as regulatory barriers increase.

4. Crowdsourcing solutions: inspiration and know-how from patients

The search for solutions for the treatment of various pathological conditions and diseases is no longer only in the hands of pharmaceutical companies. With open access to a variety of scientific data, patients today are ready to seek additional sources of information, and therefore they no longer rely solely on what pharmaceutical companies recommend and their R&D departments approve. This enables interested patients to take responsibility for their health and find a solution that would help them overcome their disease or other pathological conditions. It is not uncommon for patients to risk their

health and even their lives by agreeing to take part in clinical trials and testing new drugs in order to accelerate the process of finding an effective drug.

The importance of the patient's role in the development of modern pharmaceuticals is well illustrated by the example of Solid Biosciences, which is trying to find an effective treatment for such a genetic disease as Duchenne muscular dystrophy. “There are no specific treatments for Duchenne muscular dystrophy. There is only one drug on the market that has been approved for a small group of patients. Solid is dedicated to discovering, researching and developing the most promising approaches to tackling the disease at all stages,” said Ilana Ganot, CEO and founder of Solid Biosciences and father of a son diagnosed with Duchenne syndrome.

5. Openness of innovations VS. confidentiality

Given that the pharmaceutical industry is highly regulated, it is only natural that privacy is critical. In general, pharmaceutical companies do not share corporate information with others - data circulates exclusively through internal channels, which is strictly regulated by corporate protocols and non-disclosure agreements. This level of confidentiality, on the one hand, protects the interests of business, but on the other hand, it means a lack of openness and partnership between pharmaceutical companies, especially when it comes to the development of drugs for the most complex diseases. As a result, the cost of research and development and experimentation increases. A solution to this problem is offered by the practice of open innovation, which is already widely used by the Structural Genomics Consortium (SCG), which promotes and implements a strategy of full openness of knowledge in the field of structural and chemical biology. It is a non-profit organization that serves as a research accelerator, giving the scientific community access to all its developments without any restrictions. SCG partners with pharmaceutical companies and laboratories from six leading universities, including Oxford, the University of Toronto and the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill. Information is disseminated openly to all partners: drug request lists, research results in open access journals and experimental samples. This open-mindedness tactic is expected to accelerate the lengthy and costly drug development process for even the most severe diseases.

6. Nanotechnology

Nanotechnology in pharmaceuticals has been a very popular topic for over 20 years. By definition, nanotechnology is a field of applied science and technology that deals with the study of the properties of objects and the development of system devices at the

nanometer scale. The term "nanotechnology" was first used by Norio Taniguchi, an engineer at the University of Tokyo, in 1974 in an article on material processing. Today nanotechnology is one of the most intensively developing areas of science in a variety of industries, incl. in medicine and pharmacy. The possibilities of using nanotechnology in medicine are united by the concept of nanomedicine. The development of nanomedicine is closely related to the revolutionary advances in genomics and proteomics, which have brought scientists closer to understanding the molecular basis of diseases. There are five main areas of application of nanotechnology in medicine: delivery of active drugs, new methods and means of treatment at the nanometer level, in vivo diagnostics, in vitro diagnostics, and medical implants. Many experts in the pharmaceutical industry hope that nanotechnology will make a breakthrough in genetic engineering, medicine, diagnostics and the invention of various types of new dosage forms in pharmacy. Over the course of 10 years, the number of scientific publications on nanomedicine in the world has quadrupled. The number of patent applications for inventions is also growing, which indicates the increasing commercialization of this area. The leaders of nanomedicine, judging by the number of publications and patent applications, are currently the United States (32% of publications and 53% of applications), Germany (8% of publications and 10% of applications) and Japan (9% and 6%, respectively). But not only the leading industrial powers are striving to actively develop nanotechnology, but also developing countries, in particular in the Asia-Pacific region. There is a hope that in the near future we will live up to the time when it will be enough to swallow a tablet of nanorobots for heart surgery.

One of the many examples of advances in nanomedicine is the anti-cancer drug Genexol-PM from Samyang. Genexol-PM fights breast and non-small cell lung cancer by providing targeted transport of the active ingredient paclitaxel into tumor tissue. It is a sterile, lyophilized polymeric micellar formulation of paclitaxel that uses a colloidal carrier system for intravenous administration of the drug.

7. Personalized medicine and customization

At the moment, we buy drugs that have been developed for millions of people, without considering the genetic differences of each individual. In the near future, the patient will become an integral part of production processes in the pharmaceutical industry: based on his medical history and examination results, the pharmacist will "print" (about the possibilities of 3D printing below) individual medicines and offer additional treatment methods. In fact, this is not a new trend in health care: for example, when a muscle is stretched, the patient is prescribed an individual physiotherapy plan. Now, the same customization should happen in the pharmaceutical industry. Currently, this practice

is being implemented mainly by pharmaceutical companies specializing in oncology and genetic diseases.

8. 3D printing

3D printing in pharmacy is closely related to the trends of customization and development of personalized medicine. The rapid development of 3D printers and their adaptation for the pharmaceutical industry will soon allow pharmacists to print the medicines they need at any time and under any circumstances.

In fact, the first drug was 3D printed back in 2015. The drug is called Spritam (owned by the pharmaceutical company Aprelia Pharmaceuticals) and is intended to treat epilepsy. It is officially the first 3D printed product approved by the FDA (U.S. Food and Drug Administration) for use inside the human body and available on the mass market. A Spritam tablet is made by 3D printing layers of powdered drug and bonding them into a porous structure. This is what allows the tablet to dissolve much faster than usual, which makes it easier for patients to take during epileptic seizures, who are often prescribed large tablets that are difficult to swallow.

“After examining the potential applications of our 3D printing technology in prescription drugs, we realized the importance of comfortable drug intake for certain conditions,” summed up Don Wetherhold, CEO of Aprelia. "Spritam has revolutionized the way epilepsy medication is taken and is the first in a line of products we develop to provide patients and caregivers with complementary therapies."

The company intends to expand its line of 3D-printed drugs to fight diseases of the central nervous system and mental disorders: someday, pills for depression, Parkinson's disease, schizophrenia and others should appear on the market.

9. Artificial intelligence and cognitive computers

With the help of artificial intelligence and cognitive computers, humans will be able to collect, accumulate and classify unthinkable amounts of information in a matter of seconds. This will solve the problem that the current process of developing new drugs is too long and very expensive. Using artificial intelligence and cognitive computers, pharmaceutical companies will finally be able to conduct cognitive research and testing in

seconds, rather than decades or even longer. What's more, the speed of testing will save billions of dollars, which will have an impact on lower drug prices. Now patients who live in the hope of getting their medicine on time will be able to receive it much earlier. Plus, it could be the beginning of the end for experimentation and testing on animals or humans.

An example is Benevolent Bio. They developed an artificial intelligence-based Judgment Correlation System (JACS) that can view billions of sentences and paragraphs from millions of medical scientific studies and abstracts.

10. Telemetry in medicine and health gadgets

High technologies and artificial intelligence in medicine have led to the emergence of a new popular trend - the fashion for health gadgets and various sensors. Chips inserted into the body, contact gadgets that are worn on the body, digital tattoos, mini-robots and various other sensors will help to receive information about the patient's condition in real time and immediately send it to medical workers who can immediately indicate which medications are needed. This will make it possible to make informed and quick decisions on the prescription of drugs based on the obtained physiological data, avoiding the medical link in the chain of the traditional business model of the pharmaceutical market: patient - doctor - medicine.

For example, emulate is developing Organs-on-Chip's technology to create an integrated system that will provide highly accurate information about the internal processes of the human body. The system combines microengineering, computer technology and applications with living cells of the body, offering a new method for modeling human biology - the Human Emulation System. The company offers researchers and development teams an innovative new standard product for predicting human response to drugs, chemicals and foods with greater precision and control than current approaches to cell culture or animal testing.

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